

“Exposure Assessment in Dioxins & Dioxin-like PCBs”

ImproRisk Scientific Report

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1 Summary

Dioxins are a group of chemically related compounds that are unintentional by-products of various industrial processes, including the manufacturing of herbicides and pesticides, paper bleaching, and combustion processes such as waste incineration. The most toxic dioxin is 2,3,7,8-Tetrachlorodibenzo-p-dioxin (TCDD). Dioxins are highly toxic and can cause reproductive and developmental problems, damage the immune system, interfere with hormones, and also cause cancer. Long-term exposure to dioxins has been shown to result in severe skin disease (chloracne) and altered liver function.

PCBs are a group of synthetic organic chemicals that contain 209 individual compounds (known as congeners) with varying levels of toxicity. PCBs were used in a variety of industrial applications, including as coolants and lubricants in transformers, capacitors, and other electrical equipment. Dioxin-like PCBs are a subset of PCBs that have similar toxic effects and mechanisms of action as dioxins. Dioxin-like PCBs can cause similar health effects as dioxins, such as cancer, immune system suppression, nervous system effects, reproductive and developmental problems, and endocrine disruption.

Dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs are mainly released into the environment through combustion processes, industrial activities, and as by-products of chemical manufacturing. Human exposure occurs primarily through the food supply, particularly from animal fats in meat, dairy products, fish, and shellfish. They accumulate in the food chain due to their fat-solubility and persistence in the environment.

In the current report the dietary exposure of the target population is studied using ImproRisk model v.0.5.4. The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the dietary dioxins intake of the population in Cyprus, to compare this exposure estimate with the Tolerable Weekly Intake (TWI) of 2×10^{-6} $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ body weight (b.w.) per week and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the dietary dioxin exposure.

Mean and 95th percentile dietary dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs exposure of the Cypriot population was calculated as 3×10^{-6} and 1×10^{-5} $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ b.w. per week, respectively. It was found that approximately 42 % of the whole population was exposed over the TWI value of 2×10^{-6} $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ b.w. per week. Much higher exposure was observed for infants, toddlers and other children due to their lower body weight and may be from the consumption habits.

There was no significant difference in dioxins intake between genders and different geographical areas.

Fish (29.6%), cheese (29.5%), meat (14.1) and milk (13.4%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the dioxins intake for the whole population. For infants, milk had the highest contribution (72.7%) in dioxins exposure.

2 Introduction

Dioxins and dioxin-like compounds are a group of chemical compounds that are persistent organic pollutants (POPs) in the environment. They are mostly by-products of burning or various industrial processes or, in the case of dioxin-like PCBs and PBBs, unwanted minor components of intentionally produced mixtures. Some of them are highly toxic, but the toxicity among them varies. They are grouped together because their mechanism of action is the same. They activate the aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AH receptor), albeit with very different binding affinities, leading to high differences in toxicity and other effects. They include:

1. Polychlorinated dibenzo-p-dioxins (PCDDs), or simply dioxins. PCDDs are derivatives of dibenzo-p-dioxin. There are 75 PCDD congeners, differing in the number and location of chlorine atoms, and 7 of them are specifically toxic, the most toxic being 2,3,7,8-tetrachlorodibenzodioxin (TCDD).
2. Polychlorinated dibenzofurans (PCDFs), or furans. PCDFs are derivatives of dibenzofuran. There are 135 isomers; 10 have dioxin-like properties.
3. Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), derived from biphenyl, of which 12 are "dioxin-like". Under certain conditions PCBs may form dibenzofurans through partial oxidation.
4. Polybrominated analogs of the above classes may have similar effects.
5. "Dioxin" can also refer to 1,4-dioxin or p-dioxin, the basic chemical unit of the more complex dioxins. This simple compound is not persistent and has no PCDD-like toxicity.

Dioxins have different toxicity depending on the number and position of the chlorine atoms. Because dioxins refer to such a broad class of compounds that vary widely in toxicity, the concept of toxic equivalency factor (TEF) has been developed to facilitate risk assessment and regulatory control. TEFs exist for seven congeners of dioxins, ten furans and twelve PCBs. The reference congener is the most toxic dioxin TCDD which per definition has a TEF of one. In essence, multiplying the amount of a particular congener with its TEF produces the amount toxicologically equivalent to TCDD, and after this conversion all dioxin-like congeners can be summed up, and the resulting toxicity equivalent quantity (TEQ) gives an approximation of toxicity of the mixture measured as TCDD.

Dioxins are virtually insoluble in water but have a relatively high solubility in lipids. Therefore, they tend to associate with organic matter such as plankton, plant leaves, and animal fat. In addition, they tend to be adsorbed to inorganic particles, such as ash and soil. Dioxins are extremely stable and consequently tend to accumulate in the food chain. They are eliminated very slowly in animals, e.g. TCDD has a half-life of 7 to 9 years in humans. Incidents of contamination with PCBs are often reported as dioxin contamination incidents since these are of most public and regulatory concern.

2.1 Background

2.2 Terms of Reference

The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the dietary dioxins intake of the population in Cyprus, to compare this exposure estimate with the Tolerable Weekly Intake (TWI) of 2×10^{-6} µg/kg body weight (b.w.) per week and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the dietary dioxin exposure.

3 Data and Methodology

3.1 Occurrence data

3.1.1 Data collection and validation

Dioxins and Dioxin-like PCBs occurrence data in food were extracted from LIMS for the years 2007-2023, and are shown in Tables 3.1. The upper bound TEQ dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs was used. EFSA's assumption was applied. Low-bound scenario, Middle-bound scenario and Upper-bound scenario have the same mean values since there weren't any left-censored data. Dilution factors were applied in order to estimate concentrations for baby food. The aggregated occurrence dataset contains occurrence estimates for 76 food items.

3.2 Consumption data

Food consumption data were obtained from the EUMenu project funded by EFSA and the dietary survey was carried out in the years 2014-2018. The consumption data was the result of a survey of 1661 participants (male and female). The survey covered all five cities of Cyprus, rural and urban regions, and also all days of the week and the four seasons. The population classes and the number of participants in each class were: [a] infants: 3-11 months (269), [b] toddlers: 12-35 months (279), [c] other children: 3-9 years (300), [d] adolescents: 10-17 years (274), [e] adults: 18-64 years (275) and [f] elderly: 65-74 years (264). The consumption dataset contains 82921 occasions.

3.3 Food classification

Consumption and occurrence data were both codified according to the FoodEx2 classification system developed by EFSA. At the moment of the generation of the present report the MTX catalogue version 14.3 was applied.

3.4 Methodologies

3.4.1 Chronic dietary exposure

Dietary exposure was assessed at individual level by multiplying the average daily consumption of each food with the corresponding mean occurrence estimated for Dioxins & Dioxin-like PCBs summing up the respective intakes throughout the diet and finally dividing the results by the individual's body weight.

3.4.2 Dietary exposure assessment model

Dietary exposure assessment was performed using ImproRisk model version 0.5.4

4 Dietary Exposure Assessment

Table 4.1 presents the substance information.

Table 4.1: Substance information

key	
Chemical Substance	Dioxins & Dioxin-like PCBs
Substance Category	Contaminant
Value	2e-06 µg/Kg b.w. per week
Type of reference	Tolerable Weekly Intake (TWI)

Table 4.2 presents the exposure statistics.

Table 4.2: Summary exposure statistics of Dioxins & Dioxin-like PCBs

Scenario				
key	LB (µg/Kg b.w. per week)	MB (µg/Kg b.w. per week)	UB (µg/Kg b.w. per week)	
Min	0	0	0	
Max	6e-05	6e-05	6e-05	
Mean	3e-06	3e-06	3e-06	
95% C.I.	(3e-06 - 3e-06)	(3e-06 - 3e-06)	(3e-06 - 3e-06)	
SD	4e-06	4e-06	4e-06	
P25	1e-06	1e-06	1e-06	
Median	2e-06	2e-06	2e-06	
P75	3e-06	3e-06	3e-06	
P95	1e-05	1e-05	1e-05	
pctOver	41.5%	41.5%	41.5%	

* pctOver: Percentage of population above the reference value

Mean and 95th percentile exposure were calculated as 3×10^{-6} and 1×10^{-5} µg/kg b.w. per week (Table 4.2). It was found that approximately 42 % of the whole population was exposed over the TWI value of 2×10^{-6} µg/Kg b.w. per week, as also shown in Figures 4.1 and 4.2.

4.1 Distribution of exposure

Probability distribution

Figure 4.1 shows the probability distribution of the exposure.

Figure 4.1: Probability distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

Cumulative distribution

Figure 4.2 shows the cumulative distribution of exposure.

Figure 4.2: Cumulative distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

4.2 Mean Exposure at the MB by Gender

Table 4.3: Summary exposure statistics Gender at MB scenario.

Gender	Min	Max	Mean	95% C.I.	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
FEMALE	0	0.0000393	0.0000026	(2.3e-06 - 3e-06)	0.0000034	0.0000010	0.0000016	0.0000029	0.0000080	39.2%
MALE	0	0.0000604	0.0000030	(2.7e-06 - 3.4e-06)	0.0000039	0.0000011	0.0000018	0.0000032	0.0000108	44%

Table 4.3 and Figure 4.3 shows that there is no significant difference between the two genders meaning same food consumption habits for male and female subjects.

Figure 4.3: Mean Exposure by Gender at MB scenario.

4.3 Mean Exposure at the MB by Area

Table 4.4: Summary exposure statistics by Area at MB scenario.

Area	Min	Max	Mean	95% C.I.	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
Ammochostos	0	0.0000393	0.0000028	(1.5e-06 - 4.1e-06)	0.0000048	0.0000007	0.0000013	0.0000028	0.0000136	31.6%
Larnaka	0	0.0000305	0.0000029	(2.1e-06 - 3.6e-06)	0.0000043	0.0000009	0.0000014	0.0000023	0.0000112	33.3%
Lefkosia	0	0.0000376	0.0000030	(2.6e-06 - 3.3e-06)	0.0000034	0.0000013	0.0000020	0.0000034	0.0000094	47.3%
Lemesos	0	0.0000359	0.0000026	(2.3e-06 - 3e-06)	0.0000032	0.0000011	0.0000017	0.0000029	0.0000088	42.5%
Pafos	0	0.0000604	0.0000028	(2.2e-06 - 3.5e-06)	0.0000034	0.0000014	0.0000019	0.0000028	0.0000098	43.9%

Figure 4.4: Mean Exposure by Area at MB scenario.

4.4 Mean Exposure at the MB by Population Class

Table 4.5: Summary exposure statistics by Population Class at MB scenario.

Population class	Min	Max	Mean	95% C.I.	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
Adolescents	0.0000002	0.0000155	0.0000030	(2.7e-06 - 3.3e-06)	0.0000025	0.0000016	0.0000022	0.0000031	0.0000083	56.6%
Adults	0.0000000	0.0000216	0.0000023	(2e-06 - 2.7e-06)	0.0000029	0.0000010	0.0000016	0.0000024	0.0000077	34.4%
Elderly	0.0000000	0.0000178	0.0000019	(1.6e-06 - 2.3e-06)	0.0000027	0.0000007	0.0000012	0.0000018	0.0000068	21.9%
Infants	0.0000000	0.0000393	0.0000101	(8.8e-06 - 1.14e-05)	0.0000110	0.0000008	0.0000053	0.0000171	0.0000289	64.4%
Other children	0.0000007	0.0000342	0.0000055	(5e-06 - 6.1e-06)	0.0000048	0.0000027	0.0000040	0.0000064	0.0000149	88.2%
Toddlers	0.0000001	0.0000604	0.0000078	(6.9e-06 - 8.6e-06)	0.0000073	0.0000035	0.0000052	0.0000085	0.0000242	91.9%

In Table 4.5 and Figure 4.5 the exposure of each population class is shown. It was found that infant and toddlers had the highest mean exposure, followed by other children and adolescents showing three- or four-times higher exposure than adults and elderly. The lower body weight of these population classes is a reason for the higher exposure. Also 91.9% of toddlers, 88.2% of other children and 64.4% of the infants were exceeding the TWI for dioxins intake. Investigating the consumption data, it was observed that infants were mostly exposed due to the consumption of human milk. On the other hand, other children and toddlers were more exposed to dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs and a higher percentage exceeded the TWI, because of the consumption of fish and other food containing significant

amounts of dioxins, such as meat, milk and eggs, in amounts that due to their low body weight led to high dioxins intake.

Figure 4.5: Mean Exposure by Population Class at MB scenario.

4.5 Mean Exposure at the MB scenario by [Area and Population class]

Figure 4.6: Cross Plot

Figure 4.6 illustrates the mean exposure to dioxins by population class and geographical area. It was found that there is no significant difference between the geographical areas in all population classes. The exposure seems to be independent of the geographical area. This is because the population in Cyprus has the same food consumption habits and the foodstuffs that are contaminated by dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs are consumed by all population classes.

4.6 Contributions of different food groups to the dietary exposure

The contribution of each main food group to the total dioxins exposure for the whole population is shown in Figure 4.7. Fish (29.6%), cheese (29.5%), meat (14.1%) and milk (13.4%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the dioxins intake. Similar contribution profile was observed in all population classes with the exception of infants where milk had the highest contribution (72.7%) in dioxins exposure.

Figure 4.7 shows the contribution of food items at FoodEx Level 3

Figure 4.6: Contribution to the Dioxins & Dioxin-like PCBs Total Exposure MB.

Table 4.6 shows the contribution of food items at FoodEx Level 3

Table 4.6: Contribution to the Dioxins & Dioxin-like PCBs Total Exposure (MB). Food items at FoodEx2 Level 3 with greater than 1% contribution

Food category	Food level	Population class	Contribution to Total exposure
Milk	3	Infants	72.69%
Marine fish	3	Elderly	35.54%
Marine fish	3	Toddlers	27.61%
Marine fish	3	Adults	26.65%

Food category	Food level	Population class	Contribution to Total exposure
Marine fish	3	ALL	24.54%
Marine fish	3	Other children	24.32%
Ripened cheese	3	Adolescents	20.50%
Ripened cheese	3	Other children	17.59%
Milk	3	Other children	16.73%
Brined cheese (feta-type and similar)	3	Elderly	16.52%
Marine fish	3	Adolescents	15.00%
Ripened cheese	3	ALL	14.61%
Milk	3	Toddlers	14.52%
Ripened cheese	3	Adults	14.47%
Milk	3	ALL	13.44%
Ripened cheese	3	Elderly	12.73%
Milk	3	Adolescents	12.63%
Brined cheese (feta-type and similar)	3	Adults	12.54%
Ripened cheese	3	Toddlers	11.53%
Brined cheese (feta-type and similar)	3	ALL	10.75%
Brined cheese (feta-type and similar)	3	Adolescents	10.17%
Mammals meat	3	Adolescents	10.11%
Mammals meat	3	Adults	9.91%
Brined cheese (feta-type and similar)	3	Other children	9.54%
Mammals meat	3	Elderly	9.29%
Mammals meat	3	ALL	8.31%
Diadromous fish	3	Adults	6.98%

Food category	Food level	Population class	Contribution to Total exposure
Milk	3	Adults	6.78%
Birds meat	3	Other children	6.66%
Birds meat	3	Adolescents	6.43%
Milk	3	Elderly	6.27%
Fermented milk products	3	Toddlers	6.19%
Brined cheese (feta-type and similar)	3	Toddlers	6.16%
Mammals meat	3	Other children	6.09%
Birds meat	3	Toddlers	6.00%
Birds meat	3	Adults	5.88%
Birds meat	3	ALL	5.84%
Marine fish	3	Infants	5.77%
Shrimps and prawns	3	Adolescents	5.53%
Diadromous fish	3	ALL	5.08%
Fresh uncured cheese	3	Adults	4.95%
Cereals with an added high protein food reconstituted	3	Infants	4.79%
Ready-to-eat fruit-based meal for children	3	Infants	4.74%
Mammals meat	3	Toddlers	4.63%
Fresh uncured cheese	3	Toddlers	4.41%
Fresh uncured cheese	3	ALL	4.20%
Whole eggs	3	Toddlers	4.08%
Birds meat	3	Elderly	4.07%
Whole eggs	3	Adolescents	3.83%
Whole eggs	3	Other children	3.81%
Fresh uncured cheese	3	Other children	3.78%

Food category	Food level	Population class	Contribution to Total exposure
Diadromous fish	3	Other children	3.58%
Diadromous fish	3	Adolescents	3.49%
Whole eggs	3	Adults	3.47%
Fresh uncured cheese	3	Elderly	3.45%
Fermented milk products	3	Other children	3.42%
Whole eggs	3	ALL	3.41%
Fresh uncured cheese	3	Adolescents	3.37%
Diadromous fish	3	Elderly	3.36%
Fermented milk products	3	Elderly	2.99%
Fermented milk products	3	ALL	2.98%
Mammals meat	3	Infants	2.86%
Birds meat	3	Infants	2.85%
Diadromous fish	3	Toddlers	2.76%
Cereals with an added high protein food reconstituted	3	Toddlers	2.73%
Fermented milk products	3	Adolescents	2.68%
Fermented milk products	3	Adults	2.53%
Fish roe	3	Adolescents	2.51%
Processed cheese and spreads	3	Toddlers	2.40%
Whole eggs	3	Elderly	2.38%
Preserved or partly preserved sausages	3	Adults	1.77%
Ready-to-eat fruit-based meal for children	3	Toddlers	1.74%
Fish (meat)	3	Other children	1.70%
Shrimps and prawns	3	Adults	1.60%
Shrimps and prawns	3	ALL	1.58%

Food category	Food level	Population class	Contribution to Total exposure
Ready-to-eat dairy-based meal for children	3	Toddlers	1.56%
Preserved or partly preserved sausages	3	Adolescents	1.38%
Preserved or partly preserved sausages	3	ALL	1.25%
Mussels	3	Adolescents	1.16%
Fermented milk products	3	Infants	1.10%
Ready-to-eat mixed meal for children	3	Infants	1.01%

5 Uncertainties

The evaluation of the uncertainties in the exposure assessment of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs has been performed following the guidance of the Opinion of the Scientific Committee related to Uncertainties in Dietary Exposure Assessment. Table 5.1 presents a summary of uncertainties, highlighting the main sources of uncertainty and providing an estimate whether each source of uncertainty is likely to lead to an over- or under-estimation of the calculated dietary exposure.

Table 5.1: Summary of qualitative evaluation of the impact of uncertainties on the dietary exposure.

Sources of uncertainty	Direction ¹
Different time frame between concentration data and consumption data	+/-
Long-term (chronic) exposure assessed from few days of consumption	+
Measurement error in amounts of food consumed	+/-
Measurement error in individual body weights	+/-
Assumptions taken into account for the aggregation of occurrence data	+/-
Use of weight coefficients for non-representativeness of the population	+/-
Level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy for the calculation of the exposure	+

¹+ = uncertainty with potential to cause over-estimation of exposure; - = uncertainty with potential to cause under-estimation of exposure

A number of uncertainties can be identified regarding the selection of parameters, such as dioxins concentration levels in foodstuffs and consumption data.

The uncertainty related to the representativeness of the occurrence data for certain food commodities with respect to the number of samples is taken into account. Given the fact that the analytical results were generated with a high-resolution MS method in an accredited laboratory, this adds only slightly to the uncertainty of the analytical results.

Some potentially important extrapolation uncertainties arise since an individual survey of food consumption is used to estimate dietary exposure over a timescale longer than the

survey duration. Remaining uncertainties relate to the measurement error in amounts of consumed foodstuffs and individual body weights.

In ImproRisk occurrence and consumption data matching for the calculation of the exposure is performed based on a level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy, which may lead to overestimation of the exposure.

Furthermore, several assumptions taken into account in the preparation of the occurrence data (data from EFSA, dilution factors, aggregation) may lead to some uncertainties.

6 Conclusions

Mean and 95th percentile dietary dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs exposure of the Cypriot population was calculated as 3×10^{-6} and 1×10^{-5} $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ b.w. per week, respectively. It was found that approximately 42 % of the whole population was exposed over the TWI value of 2×10^{-6} $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ b.w. per week. Much higher exposure was observed for infants, toddlers and other children due to their lower body weight and may be from the consumption habits.

There was no significant difference in dioxins intake between genders and different geographical areas.

Fish (29.6%), cheese (29.5%), meat (14.1%) and milk (13.4%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the dioxins intake for the whole population. For infants, milk had the highest contribution (72.7%) in dioxins exposure.

Similar and comparable results were observed for the pan-European population according to EFSA's opinion, with dietary exposure values ranging between $2.1 - 46.4 \times 10^{-6}$ $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ b.w. per week [2].

7 References

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8 Abbreviations

Table 8.1: Abbreviations

Key	Description
BMDL	Benchmark dose lower limit (lower bound of benchmark dose interval)
b.w.	Body weight
LB	Lower bound
LOD	Limit of detection
MB	Middle bound
MoE	Margin of exposure
SD	Standard deviation
P25	25th percentile
P75	75th percentile
P95	95th percentile
UB	Upper bound
wcoeff	Weight coefficient

9 Appendices